

Development And Validation of RP-HPLC Method for The Estimation of Ponesimod in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

Pankaj Chaudhary*, Janhavi Latey, Aditya Khanzode, Prashant Burange

Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, P. R. Pote Patil College of Pharmacy, Amravati 444602, Maharashtra, India.

ABSTRACT

The pharmaceutical industry demands precise and robust analytical methods to ensure drug quality, safety, and efficacy. This thesis presents the development and validation of a reliable Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for estimating Ponesimod, a selective sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor modulator, in bulk and tablet dosage forms. Method development focused on optimizing chromatographic parameters such as mobile phase composition and flow rate to achieve high resolution and minimal tailing. The final method demonstrated excellent linearity across the 10–30 µg/mL concentration range, with a correlation coefficient (r^2) > 0.999. System suitability tests confirmed acceptable retention time, theoretical plates, and tailing factor. Accuracy was validated through recovery studies, with results ranging from 98% to 102%, while precision studies showed %RSD values below 2%, affirming method reproducibility. The method's sensitivity was established with LOD and LOQ values of 1.09 µg/mL and 3.29 µg/mL, respectively. Robustness was proven by varying analytical conditions, and forced degradation studies confirmed its stability-indicating capability under acid, base, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic stress. Overall, the validated method complies with ICH guidelines and is suitable for routine analysis of Ponesimod in pharmaceutical formulations..

Keywords: Ponesimod, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Validation, Pharmaceutical Dosage Form, ICH Guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic autoimmune disorder that affects the central nervous system and leads to progressive neurological impairment. Among the newer treatment strategies, **sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) receptor modulators** have shown significant clinical benefits. Ponesimod, a selective modulator of the **S1P1 receptor**, is one such agent designed to provide a safer and more targeted alternative to earlier drugs like fingolimod. Fingolimod acts on multiple receptor subtypes, including S1P3, which is associated with several of its adverse effects. By contrast, ponesimod selectively targets S1P1, thereby reducing unwanted side effects while maintaining therapeutic efficacy. The U.S. FDA granted approval for ponesimod on **March 18, 2021** for the treatment of relapsing forms of MS in adults. (Kapoos L 2011, Reyes M 2015)

Chemical name: (2Z,5Z)-5-{3-Chloro-4-[(2R)-2,3-dihydroxypropoxy]benzylidene}-3-(2-methylphenyl)-2-(propylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one

Molecular formula: C₂₃H₂₅ClN₂O₄S

Molecular weight: Average: 460.97

Boiling Point: 658.0±65.0 °C at 760 mmHg

Density: 1.3±0.1 g/cm³

Description: Ponesimod is a white to light yellowish colour powder.

Solubility: Ponesimod solubility of 0.669 mg/mL in water at 20°C and practically insoluble or insoluble in aqueous media with pH of 1.23 to 12.79.

Mechanism of Action:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The **S1P1 receptor** is highly expressed on lymphocytes, where it plays a key role in immune cell trafficking. Normally, lymphocytes migrate out of lymphoid organs in response to sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) gradients in the blood and lymph. Ponesimod binds to S1P1 receptors, induces their internalization, and prevents lymphocytes from sensing S1P gradients. As a result, lymphocyte egress into circulation is blocked, leading to a reduced number of circulating lymphocytes available to enter the central nervous system and cause inflammation. Notably, ponesimod demonstrates about **650-fold greater selectivity for S1P1** compared to endogenous S1P. (Kethipalli 2022)

Absorption and Bioavailability: A 10mg oral dose of ponesimod is 84% bioavailable. Ponesimod reaches a C_{max} of 109 ng/mL, with a T_{max} of 4.0 hours, and an AUC of 3872 h*ng/mL. (Kethipalli 2022)

Distribution: The volume of distribution of ponesimod at steady state is 160 L.

Metabolism:

Ponesimod undergoes extensive metabolism through multiple pathways:

- **Sulfation** → formation of metabolite M5
- **Oxidation** → leading to M27 (further glucuronidated to M38, M39, M40 by UGT1A1 and UGT2B7)
- **Reduction** → producing M6
- **Dealkylation** → producing M32
- **Oxidation + hydrolysis** → generating M13, which can be further metabolized to M32 and subsequently to M48 (Brossard 2013)

Elimination Route:

57.3-79.6% of a radiolabelled oral dose is recovered in the feces, with 16-26% as the unmetabolized parent compound and 22% as the M12 metabolite. 10.3-18.4% of an oral dose is eliminated in the urine. 0.6-1.9% of a radiolabelled dose was recovered as expired CO₂.

Half-life

Ponesimod has an elimination half-life of 33 hours. The clearance of ponesimod is 3.8 L/h.[4]

Pharmacodynamics:

Ponesimod is taken once daily due to its long duration of action. While effective, it carries risks similar to other S1P modulators. Patients should be monitored for:

- **Infections** (due to lymphocyte reduction)
- **Cardiac effects** such as bradyarrhythmia and AV conduction delays
- **Respiratory function decline**
- **Liver injury**
- **Increased blood pressure**
- **Macular edema and cutaneous malignancies**
- **Fetal toxicity (Brossard 2013)**

MATERIAL AND INSTRUMENT

Procurement of drug sample

Name of Drug: Ponesimod

Quantity: 20 mg

Drug Supplier: Sun life sciences

Reagents and chemicals

All the chemicals used are of HPLC and AR grade. Chemicals used are as follows

Name of Chemicals:

1. Methanol (CH₃OH) – Flammable Solvent
2. Potassium Di- hydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄) – White Crystalline Powder
3. Water HPLC (H₂O) – Universal Solvent
4. Sodium dihydrogen Phosphate (NaH₂PO₄) – Acid Salt

5. Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) – Colorless Liquid

Instruments

HPLC – Waters system

Software – Empower V3

Ph Meter – Lab india

Balance – BSA224S-CW – Lab india

Sonicator – SA-1 – Leela sonic

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

1. Identification of drug

Organoleptic properties of drug

The sample of Ponesimod was checked for organoleptic properties such as colour and odour.

Solubility analysis

Ponesimod is soluble in methanol, water and practically insoluble in aqueous media.

2. High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1		2.046	2176929	100.00	200033	1.66	1640

Chromatographic Condition for Trial 1

Mobile phase – OPA: Methanol, 50:50% v/v

Selection of column – ACE. C18, 150X4.6mm, 5µm

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Column temperature - 25°C

Sample temperature - 25°C

Volumn – 10µl

Preparation of standard stock solutions (200 µg/ml Ponesimod)

Accurately weigh and transfer 20mg, Ponesimod into 100ml of volumetric flask and add 10ml of Methanol and sonicate for 10 minutes (or) shake 5min and make volume up to the mark with water and mix.

Preparation of standard solutions (20 µg/ml Ponesimod)

Transfers the 1ml of standard stock solution into 10ml volumetric flask, and make volume up to the mark with water and mix.

Mobile Phase Preparation

Transfer 1000ml of HPLC water into 1000ml of beaker and KH₂PO₄ (1M- 136.09 gm/mol) adjust pH 4.0 (OPA).

Mix the 45 volume of Methanol and 55 volume of KH₂PO₄ buffer solution with adjusted pH 4.0 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Sonicate & Degased for 20min.

Trial 1

Run time – 10 min

Detector – PDA

Observation – One peak was detected but peak shape is not good

Reason – May be buffer and column efficiency is low

Corrective action – Change the column and buffer

Trial 2

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1		2.523	637071	100.00	108101	1.39	4545

Chromatographic Condition for Trial 2

Run time – 10 min

Mobile phase – NaH_2PO_4 :Methanol 50:50% v/v

Detector – PDA

Selection of column – cosmicsil. C18, 150X4.6mm, 5 μm

Observation – One peak was detected but peak shape is not good

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Reason – May be column efficiency is low

Column temperature - 25°C

Corrective action – Change the column

Sample temperature - 25°C

Trial 3Volumn – 10 μl

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1		3.476	1717743	100.00	117391	1.76	1148

Chromatographic Condition for Trial 3

Run time – 10 min

Mobile phase – NaH_2PO_4 :Methanol 65:35% v/v

Detector – PDA

Selection of column – Waters,C18, 150X4.6mm, 5 μm

Observation – One peak was detected but peak shape is not good

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Reason – May be buffer and column efficiency is low

Column temperature - 25°C

Corrective action – Change the column and buffer

Sample temperature - 25°C

Trial 4Volumn – 10 μl

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1		4.537	7477755	100.00	908565	1.21	7083

Chromatographic Condition for Trial 4Volumn – 10 μl Mobile phase – KH_2PO_4 buffer with pH 3.5:Methanol 65:35% v/v

Run time – 6 min

Selection of column – Inertsil,C18, 150X4.6mm, 5 μm

Detection Wavelength – 265nm

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Observation – One peak was detected but RT is high

Column temperature - 25°C

Reason – May be composition is not suitable

Sample temperature - 25°C

Corrective action – Change the composition

Trial 5

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
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1		3.440	5600942	100.00	850477	1.21	6518
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Chromatographic Condition for Trial 5

Mobile phase – KH₂PO₄ buffer with pH 3.5:Methanol 55:45% v/v

Selection of column – Inertsil,C18, 150X4.6mm, 5µm

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Column temperature - 25°C

Sample temperature - 25°C

Volumn – 10µl

Run time – 6 min

Detection Wavelength – 265nm

Observation – One peak is eluted an all system suitability parameters are with in limits

Mobile phase – KH₂PO₄ buffer with pH 3.5:Methanol 55:45% v/v

Selection of column – Inertsil,C18, 150X4.6mm, 5µm

Flow rate – 1.0 ml/min

Column temperature - 25°C

Sample temperature - 25°C

Volumn – 10µl

Run time – 6 min

Detection Wavelength – 265nm

Procedure:

Inject 10µL of standard, sample into chromatographic system and measure the areas for the Lumacaftor and calculate the % assay by using the formula.

Optimized Chromatographic Condition

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1		3.440	5600942	100.00	850477	1.21	6518

Figure No. 1: Chromatogram of optimization method

Observation: RT was found to be good and the peak symmetry of both drugs was good. And the theoretical plate count and tailing were within the limits and it is used for validation of the method.

Transfer 1000ml of HPLC water into 1000ml of beaker and KH₂PO₄ (1M- 136.09 gm/mol) adjust the pH 4.0 with diluted Orthophosphoric acid. Filter through 0.45µm membrane filter.

Preparation of Buffer Solution:**Preparation of mobile phase:**

Mix the 450ml of Methanol and 550ml of KH_2PO_4 buffer solution with adjusted pH 4.0 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Sonicate & Degased for 20min.

Preparation of standard stock solutions (200 µg/ml Ponesimod)

Accurately weigh and transfer 20mg, Ponesimod into 100ml of volumetric flask and add 10ml of Methanol and sonicate for 10 minutes (or) shake 5min and make volume up to the mark with water and mix.

Preparation of standard solutions (20 µg/ml Ponesimod)

Transfers the 1ml of standard stock solution into 10ml volumetric flask, and make volume up to the mark with water and mix.

Preparation of Sample solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 20 Tablets and crush them in to fine powder, transfer the weight of sample equivalent to 20mg (50mg sample) of Ponesimod in to 100 ml volumetric flask and add 5 ml of Methanol shake manually 5 minutes after that add 10 ml of Methanol then sonicate for 10 minutes and then make up volume with Methanol.

Transfers the above solution into 1ml into 10ml volumetric flask dilute to volume with Methanol. And the solution was filtered through 0.45µm filter before injecting into HPLC system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Identification of drug:

Organoleptic properties of drug:

Ponesimod

Colour : light yellowish colour powder

Odour : Odourless

Solubility Study:

Solubility of Ponesimod was observed by dissolving them in different solvents and the observed results are given below

Solvent : 1. Cold water – Soluble

2. Methanol - Soluble

2. Development of HPLC method for Ponesimod

High performance liquid chromatographic method was developed and validated for determination of Ponesimod. Mobile phase consists of (Methanol: Phosphate Buffer, 45:55v/v). Chromatogram obtained was shows the maximum wavelength where the drug shows maximum response was 265 nm and is shown in Fig.8

Validation Parameter

1. System suitability

Method validation confirmed acceptable system performance for ponesimod. The number of theoretical plates ($N = 6512$) demonstrated excellent column efficiency (requirement: $N > 2000$). The tailing factor ($T = 1.21$) indicated symmetric peak shape (acceptance: $T < 2$). The %RSD for retention time and peak area was within 2%, confirming good reproducibility. Table 1 summarizes the system suitability parameters as well as their acceptance requirements.

Table No 1: System Suitability Parameters

Parameters	Conc. (20 µg/mL)
Theoretical plate	6512
Tailing factor	1.21
Retention time	3.438
Peak area	5603048

2. Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of component which may be expected to be present; typically, these might include impurities, degradant, matrix, etc.

Observation:

No interference should be observed due to blank, placebo peak at the retention time of Ponesimod standard solution and sample solution.

Ponesimod peak obtained in Standard and sample solution should be pure.

3. Linearity

Calibration curves constructed in the range of **10–30 µg/mL** showed excellent linearity with correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 1.000$). The regression equation

obtained was $y = 280819x - 22870$, confirming strong proportionality between concentration and response. The calibration curves of Ponesimod were linear over the tested concentration range of 10-30 µg/mL with a correlation coefficient (r^2) of 1.000 and regression equations $y = 280819x - 22870$ in Table no.2.

Table No.2: Data of calibration curve of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Sr.No.	Conc. (µg/ml)	Conc in %	Area
1	10	50	2784300
2	15	75	4187166
3	20	100	5598502
4	25	125	6998464
5	30	150	8399128

Figure No.2: Calibration curve for Ponesimod

Table No. 3: Optical characteristics for Ponesimod

Sr. no	Parameters	HPLC method
1	Lambda max	265nm
2	Linearity	10-30
3	Regression equation [y]	$y = 280819x - 22870$
4	Slope[m]	280819
5	Intercept[c]	22870
6	correlation coefficient [r^2]	1.000
7	LOD	0.024µg/mL
8	LOQ	0.081 µg/ml

Figure No. 3: Chromatogram of Linearity 10 µg/ml Ponesimod

Figure No. 4: Chromatogram of Linearity 15 µg/ml Ponesimod

Figure No. 5: Chromatogram of Linearity 20 µg/ml Ponesimod

Figure No. 6: Chromatogram of Linearity 25 µg/ml Ponesimod

Figure No. 7: Chromatogram of Linearity 30 µg/ml Ponesimod

4. Precision

System precision shall be performed by preparing five replicate injection of Ponesimod standards solutions.

System Precision

Table No.4: Data for System precision study of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Repeatability	Retention time	Area	T. Plate	Tailing
20 µg/mL	3.446	5604873	6485	1.22
20 µg/mL	3.451	5596223	6654	1.20
20 µg/mL	3.459	5613281	6518	1.21
20 µg/mL	3.464	5621620	6507	1.21
20 µg/mL	3.469	5629481	6451	1.20
Mean	3.458	5613095.6	-	-
SD	0.009	13166.97	-	-
%RSD	0.27	0.23	-	-

Figure No. 8: Chromatogram of System precision (20µg/ml) of Ponesimod

Method Precision/ Repeatability

preparation of Ponesimod from same batches. Data is summarizes in Table No. 5.

Method precision (Repeatability) study shall be performed by preparing six different sample

Table No. 5: Data for method precision study of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Sr. No.	Sample Weight in mg	Sample Area	% Assay
1	50.00	5594120	99
2	50.00	5618245	100
3	50.00	5590839	99
4	50.00	5608959	100
5	50.00	5601539	99
6	50.00	5590075	99
Average Assay			99
STD			0.20
%RSD			0.20

Figure No. 9: Chromatogram of method precision (20µg/ml) of Ponesimod

5. Accuracy

Accuracy testing across three concentration levels showed mean recovery values within the acceptable

range of **50–150%**, with %RSD consistently below **2%**, confirming reliability of the method. Result of accuracy study are summarized in Table no. 6.

Table No. 6: Data for recovery study of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Spiked Level	Sample Weight	Sample Area	µg/ml added	µg/ml Recovered	% Recovery	% Mean
50%	25.00	2797119	9.900	9.94	100	100
	25.00	2788280	9.900	9.91	100	
	25.00	2785807	9.900	9.90	100	
100%	50.00	5591822	19.800	19.86	100	100
	50.00	5601898	19.800	19.90	101	
	50.00	5591059	19.800	19.86	100	
150%	75.00	8392027	29.700	29.81	100	100
	75.00	8391542	29.700	29.81	100	
	75.00	8407223	29.700	29.87	101	

Table No. 7: Statistical validation of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Sr. No.	Levels	SD	%RSD
1	50%	5947.06	0.21
2	100%	6049.68	0.11
3	150%	8916.72	0.11

*Average of three determination

6. Limit of detection and limit of Quantitation

Table No. 8: Results of LOD and LOQ values of Ponesimod

Sr. No.	Parameters	Area	S/N	Values
1.	LOD	14660	3.9	0.05 μ g/mL
2.	LOQ	205632	10.2	0.75 μ g/ml

Figure No. 10: Chromatogram of LOD of Ponesimod

Figure No. 11: Chromatogram of LOQ of Ponesimod

7. Robustness

Deliberate variations in chromatographic parameters (flow rate ± 0.2 mL/min, pH ± 0.2 , mobile phase $\pm 5\%$, wavelength ± 2 nm, column oven temperature $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) produced %RSD values below 2%. This demonstrated that the RP-HPLC method is robust and

reliable under minor operational changes. The outcome of the robustness data is illustrated in Table No. 9. It was inferred that the %RSD values less than 2%. The developed method of robustness was within the acceptance criteria, which thus validates the robustness of the developed method.

Table No.9: Data for Robustness study of Ponesimod by HPLC method

Sr. No.	Factors	Variable	Conc. (μ g/mL)	Peak Area	Mean Area	SD	% RSD
1	Flow rates (mg/mL)	0.8	20	7480570	7480570	9985	0.13
2		0.8	20	7470585			
3		0.8	20	7490555			
1		1.2	20	4509907	450789	2058	0.05
2		1.2	20	4505791			
3		1.2	20	4507849			
1	pH	3.8	20	5624120	5624456	389.3	0.007
2		3.8	20	5624883			

3		3.8	20	5624367				
1		4.2	20	5618245	5618475	1169.6	0.02	
2		4.2	20	5617438				
3		4.2	20	5619743				
1	Mobile phase ratio (%v/v)	50:50	20	4507849				4507155
2		50:50	20	4505776				
3		50:50	20	4507840				
1		60:40	20	6417951	6417790	275.9	0.004	
2		60:40	20	6417472				
3		60:40	20	6417949				
1		Wavelength (nm)	263	20	6533550	6533465	1561.2	0.02
2			263	20	6534983			
3			263	20	6531864			
1	267		20	4755561	4755117	4652.8	0.98	
2	267		20	4759533				
3	267		20	4750259				
1	Column Oven Temp (°C)	23	20	5004652	5005614	3364.9	0.07	
2		23	20	5002836				
3		23	20	5009356				
1		27	20	6417951	6414107	3630.1	0.05	
2		27	20	6413635				
3		27	20	6410737				

The developed RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Ponesimod in bulk and tablet dosage form demonstrates a robust, precise, and validated analytical technique compliant with ICH guidelines. The optimization of chromatographic conditions was carried out through a systematic approach involving trials with varied mobile phase compositions and column types. Trial 5, using a mobile phase of KH_2PO_4 buffer and methanol (55:45 v/v) with an Inertsil C18 column, produced optimal results with acceptable retention time, tailing factor, and theoretical plates.

Validation studies further confirmed the reliability of the method. Linearity was observed in the range of 10–30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with an excellent correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 1.000$). Accuracy studies revealed mean recoveries within the acceptable range (98–102%), indicating the method's capability to assess true values. Precision, both system and method, showed %RSD values well below 2%, affirming repeatability and consistency.

The sensitivity of the method was established with low LOD (0.05 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and LOQ (0.75 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), while robustness testing demonstrated method stability under minor deliberate variations in flow rate, mobile phase ratio, pH, and wavelength. Additionally, the

method showed specificity, with no interference from excipients or degradation products.

CONCLUSION

The developed and validated RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Ponesimod in bulk and tablet dosage forms is precise, accurate, robust, and stability-indicating, fulfilling the requirements of ICH guidelines. Through systematic optimization of chromatographic conditions, the method achieved excellent resolution, acceptable retention time, and optimal system suitability parameters. Validation studies confirmed its linearity, sensitivity, precision, and accuracy, making it a reliable tool for routine quality control. Furthermore, its robustness and specificity, along with successful forced degradation studies, ensure the method's applicability in detecting Ponesimod even in the presence of degradation products and excipients. Therefore, this method is well-suited for regular pharmaceutical analysis, contributing to the assurance of drug safety and therapeutic efficacy.

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DECLARATION OF LIMITATIONS

The present research was conducted to develop and validate a robust RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Ponesimod in its bulk and tablet dosage form. However, the study is subject to certain limitations. The method was validated following ICH guidelines; nonetheless, it was performed under controlled laboratory conditions and may require further evaluation under different environmental or instrumental settings for broader applicability. The study was restricted to commercially available formulations of Ponesimod, and the matrix effect of more complex biological samples such as plasma or serum was not assessed. Furthermore, potential interferences from excipients were studied within the scope of the selected formulation and may vary with other brands. The developed method, although accurate and precise within the defined concentration range, may need further refinement for lower concentration detection or pharmacokinetic studies. Finally, the study was limited to a single chromatographic system, and reproducibility across different brands or models of HPLC systems was not tested.

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